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The annexation policy of the Republic of Rhodesia since 1980

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Abstract

Apparently with the aim of attracting the least possible attention, the second Rhodesian republic (not to be confused with Rhodesia's legal successor, the country of Zimbabwe) made three annexations and has a fourth in the pipeline. We have explored the strategy behind these moves.

1980-2019

The Lancaster House Agreement, signed on 21 December 1979, declared a ceasefire, ending the Rhodesian Bush War; and led to the territory of Rhodesia becoming the internationally recognized country of Zimbabwe. In order to help those Rhodesians who did not want to live in Zimbabwe, especially non-African Rhodesians, in their escape and after emigration in the diaspora, a General Assembly of 1432 delegates convened in Amsterdam on 31 March 1980 under control of the Rhodesian Intelligence Service.⁴

The RIS was already in place from 1978 with the help of the United States, Chile under Augusto Pinochet and former security forces of Portugal from the Salazar era. In Washington D.C. and Santiago (Chile), the extensive political and diplomatic incompetence of the Rhodesian government was observed with considerable horror as was the actions of the Labour government in London. It was known that the British would rather let Rhodesia run into destruction by communist rebels than to forgive Rhodesia for declaring independence in 1965 and abolishing the monarchy in 1970.^{4,8}

The new Republic of Rhodesia thus already had a professional intelligence service with a paramilitary arm that was disciplined and effective. Building up the RIS and training of the staff took place in Brazil where to hand-picked Rhodesian soldiers were flown out under the protection of friendly powers. The Salisbury government was led to believe that these individuals had deserted or been captured by the enemy. While the new Republic of Rhodesia was designed as a transglobal nation that cares for all Rhodesians, wherever they reside, preparing to serve large diaspora, a squad of the Rhodesian Intelligence Agency (RIS) occupied the western lowlands of the uninhabited and Norwegian-administered island of Bouvet in the Atlantic Ocean, occupying and annexing this piece of land roughly the size of Monaco to manifest the capital city of Rhodesbury. A heliport and basic infrastructure were laid out. It was the first annexation that the Republic of Rhodesia performed, however not the last one. This was to underscore the seriousness of the establishment of the second Rhodesian republic, and the sign was silently noticed in capitals around the globe.¹²

In this context, one must take into account that Rhodesia has never given a damn whether its actions are being acknowledged by the "world community" or not. The good relations to and personal recognition of the second Rhodesian republic by the then UN Secretary General Dr. Waldheim must not be misinterpreted. This closeness is explained by intimate personal relations between then Rhodesian President James W. Scott and the Secretary General. Otherwise, the second Rhodesian republic continues its ignorance of any meta-national institution and relies its existence entirely on reconnaissance and paramilitary strength, now through the RIS, which should not be underestimated in terms of its effectiveness.^{5,6}

2019-2021

Starting around 2010, the Rhodesian government and opposition agreed on a project called Operation Zion. The intention was to create sanctuaries where Rhodesians could find a safe haven in times of global crisis. Several dozen uninhabited but habitable islands were scouted. Ultimately, Rhodesia settled on three of these islands where it could be assumed that annexation would not trigger a military response.¹³

These are:

- Jaco Island off the coast of East Timor
- Santa Luzia Island in the Atlantic Ocean
- Henderson (Sao Joao Batista) Island in the Pacific Ocean.

Jaco Island was annexed in 2019 per normal legislative procedures. There was no international opposition. Therefore, the annexation can be considered a success. Officially, it is now called Rhodesian Jaco Island and is guarded by RIS forces disguised as skippers and other local professionals. To the outside world, an image of quiet normality is apparently to be presented.^{11,13}

Santa Luzia, now Etro de Santa Luzia Island, was annexed by presidential decree in 2020. Again, there was no opposition and the annexation can be considered a de facto success.^{10,13}

The United Nations was informed of this, but is not in much of a hurry to make changes to official works and (printed) publications. From the point of view of constitutional law, however, both annexations can be considered successful for Rhodesia, since Jaco was "unclaimed" anyway and, in the case of Santa Luzia, the legal status prior to annexation was fragile. Whether the planned and publicly announced annexation of Henderson Island will be exactly peaceful and smooth remains to be seen. For although this piece of land has been uninhabited as well as unused for centuries, and there are already RIS units on the island (mostly disguised as conservationists), the British Crown considers Henderson its territory and is known for not giving anything away. The outcome of this annexation, if it takes place, remains to be seen.

As a transglobal nation that has been stable for 41 years, Rhodesia is not designed for expansion. In political science terms, the Republic of Rhodesia's annexation policy must be viewed as having always been cautious and purposeful. The conquest and annexation of the west coast of Bouvet Island (Rhodesbury) served to build the transglobal nation and as a drumbeat for politicians in the authoritative capitals. Rhodesia achieved the desired effect, although it annexed only 15% of the island's territory, "generously" leaving the remaining 85% to Norway. This message was clear and unambiguous. The successful de facto annexations of Jaco Island and Santa Luzia (Etro) serve the purpose of protecting Rhodesian citizens, as the representatives of the second republic never tire of emphasizing that they would never again allow a "catastrophe like 1980" to occur.^{1,9,13}

Summary

In summary, the following facts describe the de facto⁹ situation:

- Jaco Island and Santa Luzia were just as successful annexation operations by Rhodesia as it was in West Bouvet.
- Rhodesia does not abide by international law.
- Nevertheless, the annexations are legal because they are uninhabited islands with no established claim by another power. Those powers that could have objected have actively refrained from doing so.

Thus Jaco Island, Santa Luzia (Etro), West Bouvet Island (Rhodesbury) and possibly soon Henderson Island are de facto legal territories of the Republic of Rhodesia.^{8,9,10,11,12,13} Whether consideration is given by the UN is irrelevant under international law, since neither the islands nor the Republic of Rhodesia are members of the UN. The latter has never sought to do so because the Rhodesian constitution prohibits membership in the UN.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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